

PHOTOVOLTAIC PERFORMANCE OF DYE-SENSITIZED SOLAR CELL INCORPORATED WIRE ELECTRODE

Hee Suk Jung, Jae Hong Kim, and Tae Jin Kang*

Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul, Korea

* Corresponding author(taekang@snu.ac.kr)

Keywords: *Dye-Sensitized Solar Cell, Wire electrode, Photovoltaic characteristics, Zylon[®]*

1 Introduction

As the remainder of petroleum decreased, the interest about alternative energy resources has increased. Among the alternative candidates, solar cells are in the limelight because these offer inexhaustible resources and low environmental impact [1]. Nowadays, dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSC) is concerned as a third generation photovoltaic cell to replace inorganic solid-state solar cells thanks to their low cost, high conversion efficiency and simple fabrication process [2,3]. However, application areas of conventional DSSCs are limited due to the rigidness of the transparent conducting oxide (TCO) coated glass substrates. To overcome this drawback, flexible DSSCs based on polymer substrates become an object of attention but their efficiencies are lower than typical DSSCs due to low thermal resistance of polymer substrates. On the other hand, Fibrous flexible DSSCs based on metal wires are able to achieve both high efficiency and flexibility thanks to good interconnection of TiO₂ nanoparticles through the sintering process at high temperature. Recently, several studies have reported fibrous flexible DSSCs to extend their application areas [4,5].

In this study, we fabricated the fibrous flexible DSSCs having different TiO₂ film thicknesses and characterized their photovoltaic properties. In addition, we fabricated DSSCs using Zylon[®] wrapped around metal wire. It is appropriate material to investigate the potential of application to smart textiles because it possesses outstanding mechanical properties, chemical stability, and superior thermal resistance [6].

2 Experimental

2.1 Preparation of metal electrodes

Two titanium (Ti) wires (Sigma-Aldrich, $\varnothing = 127 \mu\text{m}$) were twisted for the working electrode ($\varnothing = 254 \mu\text{m}$) in order to improve the adsorption of dye and the handling of wires during cell fabrication process.

The twisted Ti wires were washed with acetone and uniformly coated with a commercial TiO₂ paste (13nm anatase particles, Solaronix) using a nano dip coater (MD-0408-S2, SDI Co., Ltd.). The thickness of the TiO₂ film was controlled by the number of 10 min thermal treatment at 120 °C. The TiO₂ coated Ti wires were sintered in a furnace at 450 °C for 30 min and then immersed in an ethanol solution containing 0.3 mM of N719 dye for 24 h. A platinum (Pt) wire (Sigma-Aldrich, $\varnothing = 127 \mu\text{m}$) having a twisted structure was used as the counter electrode ($\varnothing = 254 \mu\text{m}$).

2.2 Solar cell assembly

The dye-adsorbed TiO₂ film coated Ti wires and the Pt wires were inserted to poly vinyl chloride (PVC) tube which has a inner diameter of 3 mm. Polymer tubes were sealed with parafilm and epoxy resin and then filled with an electrolyte composed of 0.5 M LiI, 0.05 M I₂ and 0.5 M 4-tertbutylpyridine in acetonitrile. A schematic of the fibrous DSSC is presented in Fig. 1. The total length and active area of the cell was 2 cm and 0.0254 cm², respectively.

2.3 Application of Zylon[®] in working electrodes

We wrapped Ti wire around Zylon[®] (Ti/Zylon[®]) and then TiO₂ paste was coated on it by dip coater. To examine the possibility of Zylon[®] as an electrode substrate, we sintered TiO₂ coated Ti/Zylon[®] at 450 °C. The TiO₂ coated Ti/Zylon[®] was applied as two types. The first type was inserted into the PVC tube and the second one was not. A schematic of the DSSC used Zylon[®] as an electrode is presented in Fig. 2.

2.4 Characterization

Surface morphology of the TiO₂ coated Ti wire and the thickness of the TiO₂ film were observed by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) and open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) were measured using a solar cell QE

measurement system (K3000(IV), McScience) under AM 1.5 illumination 100 mW/cm².

3 Results and discussion

3.1 The effects of thickness of TiO₂ film

As the number of thermal treatment increased, the thickness of the TiO₂ film increased. The thicknesses of the TiO₂ films correspond to the number of thermal treatment were measured about 0.8 μm (0 trmts), 1.3 μm (2 trmts), 2.5 μm (7 trmts), 3.6 μm (11 trmts), 6.8 μm (20 trmts), and 9.5 μm (31 trmts). As shown in Fig. 3, some cracks were formed around the intersection between the two Ti wires due to the twisting stress and grew gradually with increase of thickness of TiO₂ layer. The I-V curves of DSSCs fabricated with different thicknesses of TiO₂ film are shown in Fig. 4 and their photovoltaic characteristics are shown in Fig. 5. The V_{oc} decreased with increase in TiO₂ film thickness. As the thickness of TiO₂ film increased, charge recombination between the electrons injected into the conduction band of TiO₂ and the triiodide (I₃⁻) increased. V_{oc} is determined by energy difference between conduction band of TiO₂ and redox potential of the electrolyte. Thus, decline of conduction band of TiO₂ due to the charge recombination reduces V_{oc}. The J_{sc} increased as TiO₂ film thickness increased due to the increased dye adsorption. However, when the thickness of the TiO₂ film further increased, the J_{sc} decreased significantly because charge recombination became dominant factor. The fill factor (FF) decreased with increase of TiO₂ film thickness and the conversion efficiency (η) is changed remarkably according to the thickness of the TiO₂ film. The photovoltaic parameters of DSSCs are summarized in Table 1. The fibrous flexible DSSC with 6.8 μm TiO₂ film thickness showed best performance, giving a J_{sc} of 3.38 mA/cm², a V_{oc} of 0.63 V and a FF of 0.69.

3.2 Application of Zylon®

From Fig. 6, we can see the possibility of application of Zylon® as an electrode. The first type showed better photovoltaic performance than second one. The second type has lower stability and efficiency than first one because liquid electrolyte evaporated easily.

4 Conclusions

Fibrous flexible DSSCs based on metal wires were fabricated to extend application areas. In order to

determine the optimal TiO₂ thickness of fiber-type cell, thickness of TiO₂ film is controlled by number of thermal treatment. As the thickness of TiO₂ film increased from 0.8 μm to 6.8 μm, efficiency of DSSC increased from 0.45% to 1.48%. However, cell efficiency decreased dramatically beyond the TiO₂ film thickness of 9.5 μm. Application of Zylon® to fibrous flexible DSSCs was also studied. Although the efficiency of cell applied Zylon® was still low, possibility of Zylon® as an electrode could be verified. According to the case of the second type, Zylon® applied cell should be sealed or change the type of electrolyte to improve cell stability.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by the Basic Science Research Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (R11-2005-065), Korea.

Fig. 1 A schematic of the fibrous flexible DSSC based on metal wire

Fig. 2 A schematic of the cell applied Zylon® as an electrode

Fig. 3 SEM images of Ti wire coated with various TiO₂ film thicknesses; (a) TiO₂ layer thickness - 0.8 μm and (b) TiO₂ layer thickness - 9.5 μm.

Fig. 4 I-V curves of fibrous DSSCs fabricated with various thickness of TiO₂ film

Fig. 5 Photovoltaic characteristics of fibrous DSSCs fabricated with various thickness of TiO₂ film; (a) V_{oc} and J_{sc} and (b) FF and Efficiency

Fig. 6 I-V curves of the DSSCs fabricated with Zylon[®]

Table 1. Photovoltaic parameters of fibrous DSSCs with various thicknesses of TiO₂

TiO ₂ layer Thickness (μm)	J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V _{oc} (V)	FF	η (%)
0.8	0.95	0.65	0.73	0.45
1.3	1.32	0.62	0.68	0.56
2.5	2.26	0.59	0.69	0.92
3.6	2.87	0.61	0.71	1.25
6.8	3.37	0.63	0.69	1.48
9.5	0.72	0.59	0.64	0.27

References

- [1] Chuen-shii Chou, Ru-Yuan Yang, Cheng-Kuo Yeh, You-Jen Lin, "Preparation of TiO₂/Nano-metal composite particles and their applications in dye-sensitized solar cells", *Powder Technology*, 194, pp 95-105, 2009.
- [2] Michael Gratzel, "Dye-sensitized solar cells", J.P. & P. C: Photochemistry Reviews, Vol.4, pp145-153, 2003.
- [3] B. O'Regan, M. Gratzel, "A low-cost, high-efficiency solar cell based on dye-sensitized colloidal TiO₂ films", *Nature*, Vol.353, pp737-740, 1991.
- [4] Xing Fan, Zengze Chu, Lin Chen, Chao Zhang, Fuzhi Wang, Yanwei Tang, Jianliang Sun and Dechun Zou, "Fibrous flexible solid-type dye-sensitized solar cells without transparent conducting oxide", *Applied Physics letters*, Vol.92, 113510, 2008.
- [5] D. ZOU, D. Wang, Z. Chu, Z. Lv, X. Fan, "Fiber-shaped flexible solar cells", *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*, Vol. 254, pp1169-1178, 2010.
- [6] T. Kitagawa, K. Yabuki, R. J. Young, "An investigation into the relationship between processing, structure and properties for high modulus PBO fibers", *Polymer*, Vol. 42, pp2102-2112, 2010.